

**STATE OF TECHNOLOGICAL SECURITY AND ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES OF
MILITARY ACTIONS IN UKRAINE****Bogdan Kyryliv,***Student, Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas
St. Karpatska, 15, Ivano-Frankivsk, 76019***Halyna Hrytsuliak,***PhD., Associate Professor**Student, Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas***Ira Bodnar***Teacher,**Ivano-Frankivsk Vocational College of the
Lviv National University of Nature Management***Abstract**

Since the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, environmental security under martial law has become a global issue. The possibility of humanitarian catastrophe due to hostilities creates the threat of chemical, biological and nuclear catastrophes. Most of the damaged territories are arable lands and nature reserves of Ukraine. Military action has a negative impact on the environment, but the extent of this impact is difficult to assess while the fighting continues. The undermining of the Kakhovskiy Reservoir dam by the occupying forces has been compared to Chernobyl - it is the biggest man-made disaster in recent decades. The war against Ukraine led to serious consequences for the environment: pollution of air, water, land, radiation danger due to attacks on nuclear plants. Russian aggression justifies the term "ecocide", causing systematic and deliberate destruction of natural resources, violating international humanitarian law.

The result of military conflict is massive destruction of biodiversity, pollution of water sources and danger to millions of people. The appeal of the international community to protect the environment during military conflicts and to punish those who commit crimes against nature and humanity becomes extremely important.

Keywords: man-made safety, man-made disaster, ecological consequences, conflict.

Formulation of the problem. The first and most serious tragedy of any armed conflict is its immediate consequences. Military actions, in addition to obvious human and material losses, lead to a serious deterioration of the ecological situation, which leads to further threats to the health and safety of the population. The consequences of such conflicts, including air, water and land pollution, radiation hazards, and negative impacts on biodiversity and ecosystems, need more attention and research to ensure adequate responses and prevent large-scale environmental disasters.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Taking into account the importance of existing scientific research on the issues of man-made safety and environmental consequences of military actions in Ukraine, O. Vasylyuka, O.O. Naidyonov, I. Sukhoi, E. Simonova, O. Ovchinnikova, A. Davydova, Dag Weir, etc., it is necessary to admit that today insufficient attention is paid to the assessment of the problems of environmental consequences of military actions in Ukraine.

Investigate the current state of man-made security and environmental consequences of military operations in Ukraine, identify key problems. By analyzing the available data and literary sources, make a significant contribution to the understanding of the ecological state of Ukraine.

Presenting main material. War always leads to incredible and irreparable suffering. People die, lose their health, families, friends, homes. Among the many crimes of Russia against Ukraine and the Ukrainian people, there are those whose consequences will be felt

by more than one generation of people. This mainly applies to environmental crimes, including cynically committed ecocide.

The environment is often called the silent victim of war. Burnt industrial facilities, forests, soil contaminated by mines and shells, flooded coal mines, blown-up structures, dead animals and destroyed plants are the handiwork of the weapons of the Russian occupiers, who are conducting combat operations on the territory of our country. Russia destroys the Ukrainian natural environment mercilessly and deliberately, regardless of the consequences for the lives and health of people both in Ukraine and around the world. This causes not only moral indignation, but also requires responsibility before the international community. The consequences of enemy aggression for Ukraine's ecological security have already become catastrophic. Artillery and rocket attacks by Russian forces on industrial facilities, such as oil depots and oil refineries, lead to emissions of toxic substances into the air. Significant air pollution can negatively affect people's health in the near and distant future. The war adversely affected areas rich in biodiversity, such as the Polissia in the north, the steppe landscapes in the south, and the wetlands along the Black and Azov seas. Protected natural areas that have suffered direct damage have become objects of limited access for proper maintenance due to the war. Fires have become a widespread problem, affecting more than 12,000 km² of territory, with forests covering about 7% of this area. Most of these fires occurred within 30 kilometers of the front line.

In addition, hostilities have resulted in specifically targeted damage to water bodies or their use for warfare. This includes the flooding of river floodplains during the fighting, the destruction of dams, the undermining and destruction of the dams of the Kakhovskaya HPP in June 2023, which became the largest man-made disaster in decades. The explosion destroyed 11 of the 28 sections of the reservoir. The approximate width of the breakthrough is 177 meters. A huge mass of water, the average volume of which is equal to 18,200 million m³, began to descend rapidly downstream, flooding all settlements in its path. Up to 280 tons of lubricants, which were in units and transformers of the HPP, created a film on the surface of the water and settled to the bottom of the flooded area [8]. On the very first day of the invasion, the occupiers seized the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant, which created a serious threat. The exclusion zone was under occupation for a month. And since March 2022, Russian troops have shelled the Zaporizhka Nuclear Power Plant, which is the largest in Europe. The territory of the Nuclear Power Station is still under the control of the occupiers. They not only violate the mode of operation of the station, but also use it for the location of equipment and ammunition, which creates a radiation hazard. Enemy shelling damaged buildings near the Khmelnytskyi Nuclear Power Station. Thermal power plants on the territory of Ukraine are not an exception, which are subject to regular missile attacks and significant damage, which also affects the energy system. The unprecedented presence of the military over nuclear power has drawn attention to the range of direct and indirect threats that armed conflict, nuclear and radiation security can pose. In turn, this has created serious challenges for the international nuclear security architecture and for the legal framework aimed at preventing facilities from engaging in hostilities. Many other nuclear facilities and sites with radioactive materials were also affected, including research reactors, interim and long-term nuclear storage facilities, uranium production and legacy facilities, and industrial facilities handling or processing naturally occurring radioactive materials. Many potentially dangerous radioactive sources remain unaccounted for. Violations of safety systems are key, as are obstacles to managing already existing radiological contamination. In the conflict zone, the land becomes dangerous due to minefields, threatening the life and health of civilians. The entire region becomes mined, and it may take decades to restore ecosystems and infrastructure. Russian aggression reflects an inhuman disregard for environmental and humanitarian standards. The negative impacts of this invasion include the movement of mechanized troops, the construction of fortifications and supply routes, impact craters from explosions, chemical contamination from munitions, fuel, and military equipment, and long-term contamination from explosive shells, landmines, and their destruction byproducts.

A comprehensive assessment of such damage requires on-the-spot studies and assessments of large areas of land, which have so far been carried out only in isolated cases. Larger, albeit indirect, estimates show that a third of Ukraine's territory was within 30 kilometers of the front line within a short period of time.

The damage caused to the natural environment of Ukraine will have long-term environmental consequences at the European and global levels, as well as significant social and economic consequences. Nature plays an important role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to climate change. To date, despite the widely recognized impact of war on the environment, there is a significant lack of accurate knowledge about the extent and nature of the damage. At the moment, about 80% of the contaminated territories have been neutralized, and this has become one of the environmental goals of the "peace formula" proposed by the President of Ukraine.

Destruction of ecosystems, pollution of soil and water space, reduction of biodiversity, increase in the number of pests in forests is far from a complete list of environmental problems that Ukraine will face after the end of the war. It can be assumed that the future ecological disaster in Ukraine will have not only a local, but also a regional character, since the pollution of water and marine ecosystems, groundwater with possible radioactive, chemical or toxic waste will have a cross-border impact on some European countries.

Conclusions

The restoration of nature after the war will continue for decades. The Czech publication "Blesk", based on the research of Czech and Ukrainian ecologists, reports that the restoration of nature will take at least 50 years. It is also noted that some ecosystems and populations of some animals and plants have been destroyed to such an extent that we may lose them irrevocably. Experts emphasize the problem of moving heavy military equipment and shelling, which cause fires. Due to explosions, fires and flooding of the affected areas, the water, air and soil are polluted with hazardous substances that can remain in the environment for decades. The ecological consequences of military operations in Ukraine have a far-reaching and serious impact on natural resources and people's health. One of the key aspects of these consequences is the massive destruction of biodiversity and the threat of species extinction. Large fires caused by shelling and explosions lead to extensive loss of forests and natural habitats, with further impacts on biodiversity.

References

1. Horbulin, Volodymyr The world global problem of demining: Ukrainian vector [Electronic resource] / Volodymyr Horbulin // Environmental Bulletin. – 2022. – No. 3. – P. 21-24.
2. Ecological problems of Ukraine: the consequences of the war [Electronic resource]: bibliographic index / comp. O. O. Naidyonova; Central Ukraine. national technical Univ. – Kropyvnytskyi: National Technical University, 2023.
3. Bezsonov, Yevhen The impact of the "noise of war" on the ecosystems of Ukraine [Electronic resource] / Yevhen Bezsonov // Ecological Bulletin. – 2022. – No. 3. – P. 25-26.
4. Vasylyuk, Oleksiy What should be the fate of Ukrainian territories damaged by explosions? [Electronic resource] / Oleksiy Vasylyuk, Valeriya Kolodezhna // Ukraine War Environmental Consequences

Work Group : [Electronic journal] : [site]. – 2022. – Issue 2.

5. Gubareva, Victoria Undermining Kakhovskaya HPP. What will be the consequences for the environment? [Electronic resource] / Victoria Gubareva // Ukraine War Environmental Consequences Work Group: [Electronic journal]

6. Demchyna, Andriy Ecological consequences of military aggression for Ukraine and its neighbors [Electronic resource] / Andriy Demchyna // Detectives Bureau of Journalistic Investigations: [site]. – 2022.

7. Kozachok, Alevtyna The impact of war on the environment [Electronic resource] / Alevtyna Kozachok // Compassion in farming: [site]. - August 4 2022